

DBPC-DE - Data Repository

This Zenodo repository is reserved for the DBPC-DE validation study.

Study title:

German translation, cross-cultural adaptation and psychometric evaluation of the Dutch Blended Physiotherapy Checklist

Principal Investigator:

Katja Schimske, M.Sc.

Institution:

Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus-Senftenberg, Department of Physiotherapy

Study registration:

Registration in the German Clinical Trials Register (DRKS) pending, currently in preparation.

Ethics approval:

Ethics application submitted to the Ethics Committee of Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus-Senftenberg. Ethics approval pending.

Study protocol:

The study protocol is planned for publication in physioscience and will subsequently be uploaded to Zenodo (expected: 2026).

Data availability:

Anonymized study data will be uploaded to this repository upon study completion (expected: 2028).

For questions, please contact:

Katja.schimske@b-tu.de